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THE IMPORTANCE OF ROLE-PLAYING GAMES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the peculiarities of the role of the game in the development of emotional intelligence of junior schoolchildren. It is revealed that the introduction of the game into the learning process will contribute not only to the increase of students' interest, but also to the increase of their emotionality, as well as the ability to control emotions. The game acts as the main, most frequently realised type of activity of a child, including junior school age, and, in view of this, effective application of the game within the framework of development of emotional intelligence of junior schoolchildren requires careful research and correct selection of methodological tools in order to control the degree of development of emotional intelligence. The development of emotional intelligence, in its turn, will be a guarantee of optimal development of personality as a whole.

Key words: game, intelligence learning, emotions, emotional intelligence

The development of the emotional intelligence of a primary school child is an important aspect of the formation and development of personality, since it is emotions that largely determine the child's ability to identify himself with society and to understand his own role within it. Play allows the child to fully realise the importance of harmonious coexistence of people within social groups and society as a whole.

Emotional intelligence is an individual's ability to recognise their own emotions and emotions of others, to understand and relate their own intentions and motivation of others, as well as the ability to manage emotions within the framework of current life activity and solving specific tasks [5].

The works of such foreign authors as D. Meyer, P. Salovey, D. Caruso, D. Goleman, R. Bar-On are devoted to the study of the peculiarities of the formation of emotional intelligence. Speaking about the degree of scientific development of the topic, it should be noted that the development of the emotional sphere of the child, including emotional intelligence, was the subject of close attention in the domestic concepts of developmental education, in particular, in the works of V. V. Davydov, L.V. Zankov, B.D. Elkonin.

The role that a child lives within the framework of play can influence his/her choice of certain hobbies, which, in turn, can influence the choice of future profession.

A child of primary school age, who has just left kindergarten or home environment, is in a kind of borderline state. On the one hand, he/she is still attached to these social environments, but on the other hand, he/she is moving to a new level of social self-determination. In such conditions, the introduction of games into the educational process allows to smooth the painfulness of this transition. In view of this, games are widely used at

the early stage of school education in order to increase the effectiveness of the processes of child's personality development [4]. The game used at the considered stage of school education allows not only to increase the child's interest in learning, but also to develop new characteristics of his/her emotional state [1].

Winning and losing at play is a very important part of a child's life. Play is the prism through which the child perceives the surrounding reality, the bridge between childhood and adulthood. The results achieved in the process of play are the underlying cause of a child's emotional state, his good or bad mood. Defeat in the game can cause discouragement, depression, lack of desire to achieve any goals that used to occupy the child, frustration. Victory, as a rule, inspires the child, increases his self-esteem and self-confidence, contributes to the achievement of new victories in the future. Consequently, the results achieved by a child in games used as part of the learning process will also contribute either to the child's enthusiasm or disappointment in himself/herself and rejection of further improvement in learning.

It seems possible to state that a child's emotional range is enriched as a result of his/her participation in various games. If in early childhood a child's emotions are still rather primitive and unambiguous, as he grows up he experiences more vivid and mixed emotions, which is largely due to game processes. For example, for example, team games develop in the child the habit of rejoicing or worrying not only for himself personally, but also for his team; winning the game, accompanied by the loss of friends, generates a dual sense of joy and pride for themselves with simultaneous pity for the losers. Thus, the child learns to understand the nature of his emotions, to draw cause-and-effect links between the accomplished event and his own mood, and later to influence it, that is, to be able not to give in to the rush of emotions, to control his state, which is especially important in adult life. For example, the worst result in the class on the results of solving a puzzle can provoke a child to tears, but the realisation that the others will laugh at him in this case, most likely, will stop such a violent manifestation of emotions.

Thus, the various emotions experienced by the child in connection with his or her participation in play contribute to the fact that the emotional range becomes vivid and extensive, and the emotional state becomes recognisable.

The child understands what causes certain emotions, learns to eliminate, to the best of his or her ability, the causes of bad moods, as well as to enjoy pleasant moments.

The use of play in primary school contributes to the fact that the child gradually leaves the kindergarten regime and enters a more formalised regime through the rather comfortable conditions of play. In other words, there is not an abrupt jump, but a comfortable transition, allowing a less painful experience of the new and therefore stressful stage of the beginning of the school years.

The period of learning in primary school is also important because within its framework the individual style of pupils' activity is developed, and the use of games is also important here. The level of intellectual development and the emotional factor act as essential internal conditions that ensure the regulation of activity. There is a connection between the peculiarities of students' practical thinking and different aspects of their activity results, as well as the speed of mastering labour actions and progress in theoretical disciplines.

In the process of acquiring new knowledge, new links are formed between different levels of individuality - personality, psychodynamic and neurodynamic properties. At earlier

stages of mastering an activity, personality features are more directly related to its psychodynamic and neurodynamic properties. In parallel with the way it develops, the importance of personality traits increases.

The primary role of personality traits in relation to the manifestations of temperament and nervous system functions is through self-evaluations, intellectual qualities, components of experience, and the manifestation of emotions. Personality properties, which express the attitude to activity and intellectual capabilities of the subject, are the main factors that provide regulation of activity[5].

Games are quite actively used in the educational process of primary school; moreover, we are talking not only about the game in the classical meaning of the word, but also about the game form of class organisation, about the use of logical and similar games as tasks. Many researchers put forward the thesis that the most effective for the development of both emotional intelligence and personality in general are logical games and puzzles, because they allow not only to engage the child's abilities to productive thinking, but also to develop new emotions associated with finding the right answer [2].

Logic games, puzzles, rebuses, labyrinths and other similar tasks are aimed at developing new skills that are necessary both in learning activities and in future life.

Solving tasks of game character within the framework of the lesson develops in pupils a competitive spirit, promotes the emergence of their need to achieve victory, to beat their classmates, to become the best, which is also important for the further formation of personality. Emotions experienced by a child at the moment of achieving any success play an extremely important role, as they set him/her up for new achievements[6].

Thus, the role of play in the development of the emotional component of a child's life activity and his emotional intelligence is as follows [3]:

- the possibility of identifying oneself with other members of society, realising oneself as a part of society;
- the possibility of trying on a social role;
- the possibility of accepting social rules, developing the ability to obey them and realising the necessity of such obedience;
- Formation of a line of behaviour in accordance with the accepted rules of life in society;
- formation of new skills and abilities and related formation of pride in oneself, emergence of new, previously unexperienced emotions.

It should be noted that one of the characteristics of the younger school age is the change in the structure of the child's emotional processes. Thus, if in early childhood the manifestation of emotions is extremely bright and is accompanied by vegetative and motor reactions (screaming, squealing, fighting, falling on the floor), then at the beginning of the school period these reactions are blunted, and in general, despite individual manifestations of emotions and preservation of some capriciousness, the child's behaviour becomes more restrained [5]. The manifestation of a child's emotions, for the most part, becomes tied to specific situations experienced by him/her.

The child's emotionality at the beginning of the school period is not characterised by increased affectivity and unregulated outbursts of conflicts; behaviour becomes more even. This is largely due to the fact that school, unlike kindergarten, is perceived by most children as a serious stage of life, in connection with which, responsibility for their behaviour increases, and, under the influence of school education, the desire to be a worthy member of society is

formed. Thus, the emotions experienced by a junior schoolboy, in many respects, act as the starting point of the process of personality formation; in view of this, the formation of emotional intelligence in the period under consideration acts as one of the most important parts of the child development process.

Thus, it seems possible to draw a conclusion about the key role of play not only in the development of emotional intelligence of a junior schoolchild, but also in the formation and harmonious development of his personality. The special role of the game in the life activity of a junior schoolchild is conditioned by the fact that it is in the process of the game that the child's primary adaptation to society is realised, the child identifies himself with other members of society and realises himself as a part of it. In many respects it allows to use games productively within the framework of development of emotional intelligence and emotional component of personality.

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